

The opening of the first communication and trade routes in human history

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Abstract

The article analyzes the fact that the establishment of regular communication and trade routes between countries, which connect them to each other, has changed people's thinking, worldview, attitude to the environment, especially the possibility to compare their personal life and the situation in their country with the situation in other countries. done

Key words: territory, road, caravan, thinking, economy.

INTRODUCTION

As communication routes between territories were discovered, the number of people passing through them increased over time. Over the years, centuries, these roads have become permanent roads ¹. In particular, the Asian continent is considered the region where ancient roads were created. According to historical sources, "one of the ancient caravan trade routes was called the La'l route." This road was opened in the 3rd-2nd millennium BC. The reason why the road is called

¹ Salimov Bakhridin Lutfullaevich. The Importance of Sea Transport in the Communication System. WEB OF SYNERGY: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. 2023. Volume 2 Issue 1, 272-275.

"La'al road" is the transportation of precious lapis lazuli stone. It is also called lojuard. "Lal road" started from Pamir mountain and passed through Iran, Mesopotamia and Egypt. Objects made of lapis lazuli were even found in the mausoleums (mahrams) of Egyptian pharaohs.

Another famous ancient trade route is called "King's Road". It was founded and controlled by the kings of Iran. The "King's Road" had two directions, the first connected different cities along the Mediterranean Sea with Iran, and the second went through Iran and Bactria to Altai and India.

MAIN PART

As can be seen from the above quote, the first trade caravan routes originated in Asia and these routes covered a large part of the continent. The existence of these roads caused positive changes in the social-economic, cultural-educational life of Asian peoples². Influenced the formation and development of the principles of statehood. The creation of the trade system, which is the basis of economic relations, is also closely related to the means of communication. At first, trade was carried out in the form of barter, and later it was carried out in the form of coins made of metals such as gold and silver. The discovery of money and the beginning of its use led to unprecedented consequences in social relations. The growing interest in money and other material wealth led to the formation of classes, castes and categories that have been a constant companion of mankind for thousands of years. The existence of these is the basis for the urgent problem of ensuring social

² Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Толмасбек Анвар Ўғли Шодмонов, Улуғбек Жеткербай Ўғли Уразбаев (2022). МАМЛАКАТНИНГ БАРҚАРОР ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАБ БЕРИШДА ЙЎЛЛАРИНИНГ ТУТГАН ЎРНИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 309-314.

justice among them to be always on the agenda ³.

Records and material monuments from the past indicate that between the ancient East and the West, there was a "Pasture Road", which was considered a northern trade route that passed between the vast expanses of modern northern China, Mongolia, Russia's Siberia, the central part of Russia, and connected the European territories, where nomadic peoples lived. The material evidence found in the settlements found in these lands confirms that these areas were in contact with each other. With a history of several thousand years, this "Way of Grasslands" is indicated in Chinese sources as ("Tsavyuan lu") ⁴. The nomadic cattle-breeding peoples who lived along this road used this road for trade. It is also reported that they exchanged various articles made of precious metals and stones for various products carried by merchants, including silk fabrics. By the way, silk fabrics were also transported from China to the West through this route. However, it is not correct to consider this road as one direction of the "Great Silk Road" or to confuse them with each other. Because they are separate paths. A number of Chinese scientists have also approved this conclusion⁵.

The establishment of regular communication and trade routes between countries, which connect them to each other, has also changed people's thinking,

³ Salimov Bakhridin Lutfullaevich. The Importance of Sea Transport in the Communication System. WEB OF SYNERGY: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. 2023. Volume 2 Issue 1, 272-275.

⁴ Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.

⁵ Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.

outlook, and attitude towards the environment⁶. In particular, the opportunity to compare one's personal life and the situation in one's country with the situation in other countries has taught people to live sometimes with envy and sometimes with gratitude. Because even at that time, the standard of living of the peoples of the world was not the same as it is now. Some peoples' habitats were located in a very good natural environment, while there were also peoples living in unfavorable climatic conditions. Also, while the same peoples live in harmony, harmony, peaceful, happy and prosperous life, some of them lived in disunity, constant enmity and turmoil, and misery. In general, the territories and peoples of the world were diverse and colorful even at that time. Beachgoers, guides and merchants who saw this and traveled the country made the necessary conclusions for themselves. Why, they had the opportunity to compare and contrast each other. In a sense, many of these people were the ones who brought news and discoveries to their countries. This kind of mutual exchange of ideas and experiences is important for the perspective of countries and peoples⁷.

One of the necessary needs in the framework of social relations is the creation of a communication system. This need is the need for people to create deterministic relationships, first with each other, then families, clans, then tribes, states, and finally regions. The same aspect was the initial factor that formed

⁶ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Толмасбек Анвар Ўғли Шодмонов, Улуғбек Жеткербай Ўғли Уразбаев (2022). МАМЛАКАТНИНГ БАРҚАРОР ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАБ БЕРИШДА ЙЎЛЛАРНИНГ ТУТГАН ЎРНИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 309-314.

⁷ Salimov Bakhriddin Lutfullaevich. The Importance of Sea Transport in the Communication System. WEB OF SYNERGY: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. 2023. Volume 2 Issue 1, 272-275.

communication in the field of road transport⁸.

CONCLUSION

Searching and finding ways to go to other countries were the most important among the objectives: conducting trade, diplomatic, social, cultural relations; pursuing military and political goals. Communication paths also developed from the bottom up, from simple to complex, according to philosophical laws. The scope of the roads, which were initially formed within a small area, also expanded. Some roads that appeared within a certain clan and tribe developed into intercontinental roads. The first trade caravan routes appeared in Asia, and these routes covered a large part of the continent. The establishment of regular communication and trade routes between countries based on the principle of determinism caused positive changes in people's thinking, worldview, attitude to the environment, and the social-economic, cultural-educational life of their people.

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⁸ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Толмасбек Анвар Ўғли Шодмонов, Улуғбек Жеткербай Ўғли Уразбаев (2022). МАМЛАКАТНИНГ БАРҚАРОР ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАБ БЕРИШДА ЙЎЛЛАРНИНГ ТУТГАН ЎРНИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 309-314.

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